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Investigation of Sports Sciences Faculty Students' Motivation for Participation in Physical Activity in Terms of Various Variables

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Abstract

This research was carried out in order to examine the motivation of the students of the faculty of sports sciences for participation in physical activity in terms of various variables. In this context, the general survey model, which is consistent with the main purpose of the study was used in this quantitative study. The sample of the study consists of a total of 479 students, of which 214 are female and 265 are male. In the creation of the sample, it was benefited from convenience sampling method which is one of the non-probabilistic sampling approaches. Questionnaire form was used as data collection tool and this form consists of two parts. In the first part of the questionnaire, there is the "Personal Information Form," and in the second part, there is the "Motivation Scale for Participation in Physical Activity." The illustrative statistics of the raw data obtained through this form were firstly calculated by considering the data type. Then, the reliability of the scale dimensions related to the obtained data was investigated and the difference and correlation tests were used in statistical evaluations. Accordingly, significant differences were found in the variables of gender, mother education level and active sports status. However, there was no significant difference found in the scale dimensions within the scope of the father's education level, the place of residence with the family, the licensed sportsman status and the national sportsman status. In addition to this, it was observed that there were negative and low-level significant correlations between the age variable and individual causes and the motivation for participation in physical activity (total) dimensions. On the other hand, no significant correlation was found between personal income level and family income level variables and scale dimensions. As a result, the motivation of the students of the faculty of sports sciences for participation in physical activity within the scope of various variables is described as it exists.

Keywords: Sport Sciences, Student, Physical Activity, Motivation, Motivation for Participation in Physical Activity

1. Introduction

Physical activity is defined as any bodily movement produced by skeletal muscles that results in energy expenditure (Caspersen, Powell & Christenson, 1985). According to another definition, any movement of the body

that results from skeletal muscle contraction and increases the total body energy expenditure above the resting state is accepted as physical activity (Yuede et al., 2018). In this context, various activities such as walking, running, mowing the lawn, gardening can be considered as physical activities. In addition, the physical activity intensity spectrum can be expressed as light-intensity physical activity (<3 MET), moderate-intensity physical activity (3-6 MET), and vigorous intensity physical activity (>6 MET) (Pate et al., 1995). In this respect, the correlation between a sedentary life and non-communicable diseases is considered to be important.

Non-communicable chronic diseases such as cardiovascular disease, cancer, diabetes and chronic respiratory disease are now considered a major public health problem. These diseases are the leading causes of death worldwide and account for more than 70% of deaths worldwide (WHO, 2020). In this context, it is thought that psychologic negativities are important as well as physiological negativities (Kim, 2022). In addition to their negative effects on quality of life, these diseases reduce productivity and cause workforce losses (Malta et al., 2020). In children and adolescents, these diseases negatively affect school readiness by creating negativities in various areas (social, emotional, language, cognitive and physical) (Bell et al., 2016). Therefore, students affected by these diseases are at higher risk of facing poor educational outcomes (Barnett et al., 2018). In addition, physical activities are one of the activities that contribute to the improvement of the health status of the individual by promoting a healthy lifestyle, disease prevention, personal satisfaction and self-actualization (Mehri et al., 2016). In this context, increasing physical activity and reducing sedentary life are important behavioral changes to improve lifelong health (Piercy et al., 2018). When these behavioral changes are considered on the axis of lifestyle, this is a kind of a type of living style that can be measured as healthy or unhealthy according to the personal behavior preferences of individuals (Almutairi et al., 2018). A health-promoting lifestyle includes self-directed behaviors that are an integral part of an individual's healthy lifestyle and aim to protect and improve the individual's health and well-being (Polat et al., 2016). In this respect, it can be said that a lifestyle that includes regular physical activities can have positive effects on both physiologic and psychological states (Kim, 2022).

When the explanations are considered in the context of individuals studying in sports sciences, it is thought that physical activities have an important place in both in-class and extra-curricular activities. In this respect, it is important to have information about the level of motivation of students in today's sports sciences for participation in physical activity and the variables that affect this motivation. In this context, when the relevant literature is examined, it is seen that there are a limited number of studies for students in sports sciences in Turkey (see Karaca, 2020; Ceylan et al., 2021). However, this research was carried out with expanded variables and data set in order to reach detailed results. Therefore, it is thought that the results of the research will contribute to filling the gap in the relevant literature. In the study, it was aimed to examine the motivation of the students of the faculty of sports sciences for participation in physical activity in terms of various variables.

2. Method

2.1 Research Model

In general, it is aimed to describe the existing situation related to the subject of the study by photographing in survey research (Buyukozturk et al., 2020). Therefore, this quantitative research was designed with the general survey model consistent with the main purpose.

2.2 Research Group

Participants were selected from a total of 1135 students, 354 female and 781 male, at the Faculty of Sports Sciences of Bartın University. In this context, the sample of the research consists of a total of 479 students, of which 214 are female and 265 are male. In this framework, the sample was created using the convenience sampling method. Therefore, it is understood that the acceptable sample size for the research population has been reached (see Sekaran & Bougie, 2016).

2.3 Data Collection Tools

The questionnaire form, which was created by considering the main purpose of the research, was applied face to face to the participants in the sample, on a voluntary basis. During the application phase of the questionnaire, necessary explanations were given to the participants and accordingly the participants were ensured to answer the form correctly. This questionnaire consists of two parts, the first part includes the “Personal Information Form” and the second part includes the “Motivation Scale for Participation in Physical Activity.”

2.3.1 Personal Information Form

In the Personal information form, there are expressions created to reach information such as status, participants' gender, age, personal income level, family income level (excluding personal income), mother's education level, father's education level, place of residence with the family, active sports status, licensed sportsman status and national sportsmanship.

2.3.2 Motivation Scale for Participation in Physical Activity

Tekkursun-Demir and Cicioglu (2018) developed the “Motivation Scale for Participation in Physical Activity” in order to measure the motivation of participants for participation in physical activity. Data on the development process of the scale were obtained from 308 high school students studying at Ödemiş Anatolian High School and Ödemiş Chamber of Commerce Anatolian High School in Ödemiş district of İzmir province in Turkey in the 2016-2017 academic year. The scale consists of 16 items and is in five-point Likert type. It consists of three sub-dimensions: individual causes, environmental causes and non-casuality. The validity of the scale was evaluated with exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses. As a result of the exploratory factor analysis, the scale form explains 54.69% of the total variance. As a result of the DFA, it was seen that the 3-factor structure of this 16-item scale was confirmed. In addition, internal consistency (Cronbach's Alpha) and Spearman Brown split-half reliability coefficients were used to determine the reliability of the scale. Cronbach's Alpha values of the dimensions of the scale range from 0.82 to 0.89. Spearman Brown two-half reliability coefficients take values between 0.75 and 0.82. As a result, it was understood that the scale is a reliable and valid measurement tool (Tekkursun-Demir & Cicioglu, 2018).

2.4 Data Analysis

IBM SPSS version 23.0 was used for data analysis. It was decided whether the data exhibited a normal distribution, by examining the skewness and kurtosis values. In this direction, descriptive statistics were calculated by taking into account the type of data obtained by using the questionnaire. In addition, t-Test and One Way ANOVA were used for statistical calculations of the obtained data, and Spearman Rank Correlation Analysis was used for correlation evaluations. In statistical evaluations, the level of relevance was determined as 0.05.

3. Findings

In this part of the research, the findings obtained as a result of the analysis of the relevant data were presented and interpreted in the form of tables.

Table 1: Frequency and Percentages of Variables

Variable	Group	f	%
Gender	Female	214	44,7
	Male	265	55,3
Actively Doing Sports	Yes	280	58,5
	No	199	41,5
Licensed Athletic Status	Yes	260	54,3
	No	219	45,7
National Sportsman Status	Yes	59	12,3
	No	420	87,7
Residence place with Family	Village	62	12,9
	Town	17	3,5
	County Town	176	36,7
	City Center	224	46,8

Mother Education Level	Not Literate	75	15,7
	Literate	23	4,8
	Primary School	202	42,2
	Secondary School	80	16,7
	High School	82	17,1
	University	17	3,5
Father Education Level	Not Literate	18	3,8
	Literate	21	4,4
	Primary School	162	33,8
	Secondary School	106	22,1
	High School	132	27,6
	University	40	8,4
Total	479	100,0	

When Table 1 is examined, it is seen that the number of men regarding the participants is higher than the number of women. In addition, it has been determined that the number of those who do sports actively is higher than the number of those who do not and the number of those who are licensed athletes is higher than the number of those who do not. However, the number of national athletes was lower than the number of non-athletes. In addition, it has been found that the majority of the participants resided in the city center with their families and the highest number of participants was in the primary school group in terms of parental education level.

Table 2: Age, Descriptive Statistics of Personal Income Level and Family Income Level Variables

Variable	n	Mean	Median	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum	Skew	Kurtosis
Age	473	21,9	22	2,864	17	39	2,111	8,058
Personal Income Level (TL)	375	1211,58	700	1281,397	50	8000	2,989	10,189
Family Income Level (Excluding Personal Income - TL)	452	3492,85	3000	2264,73	200	25000	3,204	21,139

When Table 2 is examined, it is seen that the mean age variable of the participants is 21.9 and the standard deviation is 2.864, mean of personal income level variable is 1211.58 and standard deviation is 1281.397, the average of the family income level (excluding personal income) variable is 3492.85 and its standard deviation is 2264.73. In addition, it was assumed that these variables do not exhibit normal distribution in terms of skewness and kurtosis values (see George & Mallery, 2010).

Table 3: Reliability Analysis Results of Scale Sub-Dimensions

Dimensions	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
Individual Causes	,736	6
Environmental Causes	,736	6
Non- casualty	,610	4
Motivation for Participation in Physical Activity (Total)	,772	16

According to Table 3, in terms of internal consistency coefficients (Cronbach's alpha) calculated within the scope of the research, individual causes ($\alpha=0.736$), environmental causes ($\alpha=0.736$), non-causality ($\alpha=0.610$), and motivation for participation in physical activity (total) ($\alpha=0.772$) dimensions were found to be reliable.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of Scale Dimensions

Dimensions	n	Mean	Median	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum	Skew	Kurtosis
Individual Causes	479	4,6566	4,8333	0,43347	3	5	-1,439	1,919
Environmental Causes	479	4,0264	4,1667	0,75972	1,83	5	-0,585	-0,291
Non- casualty	479	1,3267	1	0,47669	1	3	1,583	1,906
Motivation for Participation in Physical Activity (Total)	479	4,4245	4,5	0,42263	2,94	5	-0,625	-0,02

According to Table 4, the mean score of the individual causes sub-dimension was 4.6566 and the standard deviation was 0.43347; the mean score of the environmental causes sub-dimension was 4.0264 and the standard deviation was 0.75972; the mean score of the sub-dimension of non-casuality was 1.3267 and the standard deviation was 0.47669; The mean score of the motivation for participation in physical activity (total) dimension was found to be 4.4245 and the standard deviation was 0.42263. In addition, it can be said that the individual causes of the participants in the context of the scale and their motivation for participation in physical activity are at a very high level, as well as a high level of environmental causes. However, it can be stated that the level of non-casuality is very low. In addition, in terms of skewness and kurtosis values, it is assumed that the scale dimensions exhibit normal distribution (see George & Mallery, 2010).

Table 5: Frequency and Percentages of Participants' Levels of Motivation for Participation in Physical Activity

Level	f	%
Too low	-	-
Low	-	-
Middle	1	,2
High	92	19,2
Too high	386	80,6
Total	479	100,0

When Table 5 is examined, it is seen that the majority of the participants (80.6%) have a very high level of motivation for participation in physical activity, while there are no participants in the too low and low groups.

Table 6: t-Test Results According to Gender Variable

Dimensions	Gender	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	t	p
Individual Causes	Female	214	4,6815	,45181	477	1,130	,259
	Male	265	4,6365	,41784			
Environmental Causes	Female	214	4,0569	,78574	477	,787	,432
	Male	265	4,0019	,73862			
Non-casuality	Female	214	1,2699	,43188	477	-2,357*	,019
	Male	265	1,3726	,50617			
Motivation for Participation in Physical Activity (Total)	Female	214	4,4594	,42736	477	1,629	,104
	Male	265	4,3962	,41745			

*p<0,05

When Table 6 is examined, it is seen that there is a statistically significant difference in favor of men in the sub-dimension of non-casuality according to the gender variable ($t_{(477)}=-2.357$; $p<0.05$). On the other hand, it was determined that there was no statistically significant difference in the mean scores of individual causes, environmental causes and motivation for participation in physical activity (total) dimensions according to the gender variable ($p>0.05$).

Table 7: Results of Correlation Analysis Between Age, Personal Income Level and Family Income Level Variables and Scale Dimensions

Variables		Individual Causes	Environmental Causes	Non-casuality	Motivation for Participation in Physical Activity (Total)
Age	r	-,004	-,134*	-,006	-,091*
	p	,933	,004	,900	,049
	n	473	473	473	473
Personal Income Level	r	,016	-,043	-,024	-,034
	p	,761	,406	,643	,517
	n	375	375	375	375
Family Income Level (Excluding Personal Income)	r	-,059	-,081	-,026	-,082
	p	,214	,084	,583	,082
	n	452	452	452	452

*p<0,05

When Table 7 is examined, it is seen that there are negative and low-level statistically significant correlations between the age variable and individual causes ($r=-0.134$) and motivation for participation in physical activity (total) ($r=-0.091$) ($p<0.05$). However, no statistically significant correlation was found between the dimensions of

the motivation for participation in physical activity scale and the variables of personal income level and family income level (excluding personal income) ($p>0.05$).

Table 8: ANOVA Results According to Mother Education Level Variable

Dimensions	Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	F	p	Significant Difference
Individual Causes	Not Literate (1)	4,7356	,44780	478	,925	,464	---
	Literate (2)	4,5725	,50957				
	Primary School(3)	4,6271	,44928				
	Secondary School (4)	4,6729	,44091				
	High School (5)	4,6545	,36738				
	University (6)	4,7059	,30917				
Environmental Causes	Not Literate (1)	4,0400	,73819	478	3,049*	,010	1>6
	Literate (2)	4,0652	,72777				3>6
	Primary School (3)	4,0924	,74590				4>6
	Secondary School (4)	4,0667	,72168				
	High School (5)	3,9329	,78779				
	University (6)	3,3922	,86791				
Non-casuality	Not Literate (1)	1,3033	,43553	478	,439	,821	---
	Literate (2)	1,3696	,51051				
	Primary School (3)	1,3280	,48847				
	Secondary School (4)	1,2781	,42096				
	High School (5)	1,3628	,51990				
	University (6)	1,4118	,52990				
Motivation for Participation in Physical Activity (Total)	Not Literate (1)	4,4650	,38558	478	1,595	,160	---
	Literate (2)	4,3967	,49090				
	Primary School (3)	4,4378	,42721				
	Secondary School (4)	4,4578	,40477				
	High School (5)	4,3796	,43599				
	University (6)	4,1838	,40593				

* $p<0,05$

When Table 8 is examined, it is seen that there is a statistically significant difference within the framework of the environmental causes sub-dimension according to the mother's education level variable ($F_{(478)}=3,049$; $p<0.05$). These significant differences were between "Not Literate" and "University," "Primary School" and "University," and "Secondary School" and "University", and all of these differences were found to be against the university group. However, in the context of the mother's education level variable, it is seen that there is no statistically significant difference in the scores of individual causes, non-casuality and motivation for participation in physical activity (total) dimensions ($p>0.05$).

Table 9: ANOVA Results According to Father Education Level Variable

Dimensions	Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	F	p	Significant Difference
Individual Causes	Not Literate (1)	4,6296	,55881	478	,693	,629	---
	Literate (2)	4,6667	,51099				
	Primary School (3)	4,6944	,41506				
	Secondary School (4)	4,6698	,38763				
	High School (5)	4,6263	,46649				
	University (6)	4,5750	,41164				
Environmental Causes	Not Literate (1)	4,0463	,95624	478	,791	,557	---
	Literate (2)	4,1667	,50553				
	Primary School (3)	4,0710	,75634				
	Secondary School (4)	4,0346	,75302				
	High School (5)	3,9975	,76056				
	University (6)	3,8375	,80904				
Non-casuality	Not Literate (1)	1,2639	,46552	478	2,311*	,043	There was no statistically significant difference between the groups after the Post Hoc Test (Hochberg GT2).
	Literate (2)	1,5000	,54199				
	Primary School (3)	1,2670	,41435				
	Secondary School (4)	1,3373	,50124				
	High School (5)	1,3182	,48655				
	University (6)	1,5063	,54151				
Motivation for Participation in Physical Activity (Total)	Not Literate (1)	4,4375	,53379	478	1,417	,217	---
	Literate (2)	4,4375	,38931				
	Primary School (3)	4,4703	,42029				
	Secondary School (4)	4,4298	,41910				
	High School (5)	4,4044	,41230				
	University (6)	4,2781	,42648				

* $p<0,05$

When Table 9 is examined, it is seen that there is no statistically significant difference between the groups after the “Hochberg’s GT2” post hoc test, although it was determined that there was a statistically significant difference within the framework of the sub-dimension of non-casuality according to the father education level variable. Therefore, it was found that there was no statistically significant difference in terms of the scores of the dimensions of the motivation for participation in physical activity in the context of the father’s education level variable ($p>0.05$).

Table 10: ANOVA Results According to the Variable of Residence Place with the Family

Dimensions	Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	F	p	Significant Difference
Individual Causes	Village	4,5430	,50762	478	2,725*	,044	There was no statistically significant difference between the groups after the Post Hoc Test (Hochberg GT2).
	Town	4,4902	,48402				
	County Town	4,6856	,41666				
	City Center	4,6778	,41521				
Environmental Causes	Village	3,9677	,85509	478	,458	,712	---
	Town	3,8824	,73069				
	County Town	4,0625	,74506				
	City Town	4,0253	,74810				
Non-casuality	Village	1,4597	,54734	478	2,056	,105	---
	Town	1,3824	,45171				
	County Town	1,3139	,46194				
	City Center	1,2958	,46560				
Motivation for Participation in Physical Activity (Total)	Village	4,3266	,48537	478	2,007	,112	---
	Town	4,2941	,36894				
	County Town	4,4521	,41735				
	City Center	4,4397	,40887				

* $p<0,05$

When Table 10 is examined, it is seen that there is no statistically significant difference between the groups after the “Hochberg’s GT2” post hoc test, although it was determined that there was a statistically significant difference in the individual causes sub-dimension according to the variable of residence place with the family. Therefore, it was found that there was no statistically significant difference in terms of the scores of the scale of motivation for participation in physical activity in the context of the variable of residence with the family ($p>0.05$).

Table 11: t-Test Results According to Actively Doing Sports Variable

Dimensions	Actively Doing Sports	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	t	p
Individual Causes	Yes	280	4,6994	,41360	477	2,580*	,010
	No	199	4,5963	,45421			
Environmental Causes	Yes	280	4,0637	,72064	477	1,274	,203
	No	199	3,9740	,81048			
Non-casuality	Yes	280	1,3071	,48113	477	-1,066	,287
	No	199	1,3543	,47019			
Motivation for Participation in Physical Activity (Total)	Yes	280	4,4594	,40776	477	2,153*	,032
	No	199	4,3753	,43905			

* $p<0,05$

When Table 11 is examined, it is seen that there are statistically significant differences in favor of those who do sports actively in the dimensions of individual causes ($t_{(477)}=2,580$) and motivation for participation in physical activity (total) ($t_{(477)}=2,153$) according to the variable of doing sports actively ($p<0.05$). On the other hand, it was found that there was no statistically significant difference in terms of the mean scores of the environmental causes and irrationality sub-dimensions according to the variable of actively doing sports ($p>0.05$).

Table 12: t-Test Results According to Licensed Athlete Status Variable

Dimensions	Licensed Athlete Status	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	t	p
Individual Causes	Yes	260	4,6827	,41277	477	1,438	,151
	No	219	4,6256	,45583			
Environmental Causes	Yes	260	4,0660	,74003	477	1,243	,214
	No	219	3,9795	,78155			
Non-casuality	Yes	260	1,3346	,48635	477	,395	,693
	No	219	1,3174	,46590			
Motivation for Participation in Physical Activity (Total)	Yes	260	4,4471	,40560	477	1,280	,201
	No	219	4,3975	,44142			

When Table 12 is examined, it has been determined that there is no statistically significant difference in terms of the mean scores of the dimensions of the motivation for participation in physical activity according to the variable of licensed athlete status ($p>0.05$).

Table 13: t-Test Results According to Variable of National Athletic Status

Dimensions	National Athletic Status	n	Mean	Std. Deviation	df	t	p																																
Individual Causes	Yes	59	4,5734	,48962	477	-1,576	,116																																
	No	420	4,6683	,42433				Environmental Causes	Yes	59	3,9831	,71699	477	-,468	,640	No	420	4,0325	,76615	Non-casualty	Yes	59	1,2881	,50175	477	-,664	,507	No	420	1,3321	,47344	Motivation for Participation in Physical Activity (Total)	Yes	59	4,3867	,44837	477	-,733	,464
Environmental Causes	Yes	59	3,9831	,71699	477	-,468	,640																																
	No	420	4,0325	,76615				Non-casualty	Yes	59	1,2881	,50175	477	-,664	,507	No	420	1,3321	,47344	Motivation for Participation in Physical Activity (Total)	Yes	59	4,3867	,44837	477	-,733	,464	No	420	4,4298	,41918								
Non-casualty	Yes	59	1,2881	,50175	477	-,664	,507																																
	No	420	1,3321	,47344				Motivation for Participation in Physical Activity (Total)	Yes	59	4,3867	,44837	477	-,733	,464	No	420	4,4298	,41918																				
Motivation for Participation in Physical Activity (Total)	Yes	59	4,3867	,44837	477	-,733	,464																																
	No	420	4,4298	,41918																																			

When Table 13 is examined, it has been determined that there is no statistically significant difference in terms of the mean scores of the dimensions of the motivation for participation in physical activity according to the variable of national athletic status ($p>0.05$).

4. Discussion and Conclusion

This study was carried out in order to examine the motivation of participating in physical activity of the students of the faculty of sports sciences within the framework of the research group in terms of various variables. In this direction, a questionnaire form was created in accordance with the main purpose of the study and the data obtained as a result of the sampling application of this questionnaire form were transformed into findings by applying different statistical analyzes. In this direction, a questionnaire form was created in accordance with the main purpose of the study and the data obtained as a result of the sampling application of this questionnaire form were transformed into findings by applying different statistical analyzes. In this framework, the results obtained on the basis of the findings were detailed by discussing in line with the relevant literature. In this respect, the individual causes of the participants in the context of the scale and their motivation for participation in physical activity are very high; It can be said that environmental causes are at a high level. However, it can be stated that the level of non-casualty is very low.

It was found that there was a significant difference in favor of men in the sub-dimension of non-casualty according to the gender variable of the participants. In other words, it has been determined that men's uncertainty about why they will do physical activity or what will happen as a result is higher than women's. This result shows some amount of consistency with the results of the studies made by Guvendi and Serin (2019), Celik (2020), Ceylan et al. (2021), and Altay and Koc (2022). However, it does not coincide with the findings of the study by Gumus and Koyuncu (2022). It is thought that this situation is due to the different educational characteristics of the participants.

It was found that there were negative and low-level significant correlations between the age variable and individual causes and the motivation for participation in physical activity (total) dimensions. In other words, as the age of the participants increases, individual causes and motivation for participation in physical activity (total) levels decrease. This result is consistent with the result of the study by Celik (2020). In addition, studies carried out by Guvendi and Serin (2019) and Ceylan et al. (2021), partially consistent with the findings of the studies.

No significant correlation was found between the variables of personal income level and family income level (excluding personal income) and the dimensions of the motivation for participation in physical activity scale. The result in the context of family income level does not coincide with the findings of the study carried out by Ceylan et al. (2021). On the other hand, the result in the context of personal income level is consistent with the findings of the study by Kucuk Kilic (2020).

It was found that there was a significant difference only within the scope of environmental causes sub-dimension according to the mother's education level variable. These significant differences were between "Not Literate" and

“University”, “Primary School” and “University”, and “Secondary School” and “University”, and all of these differences were found to be against the university group. In other words, the environmental cause scores of the participants whose mothers were university educated are lower than the scores of those who are illiterate, primary or secondary school. However, it was observed that there was no significant difference in terms of the scores of the scale of motivation for participation in physical activity in the context of the father’s education level variable. The result reached in the context of maternal education level is consistent with the result of the study conducted by Altay and Koc (2022). It is also partially consistent with the findings of the study by Kucuk Kılıc (2020). In addition, the result reached in the context of father’s education level is consistent with the findings of the studies conducted by Kucuk Kılıc (2020) and Altay and Koc (2022).

It was found that there was no significant difference in terms of the scores of the motivation scale dimensions of participation in physical activity in the context of the variable of residence with the family. This result is consistent with the result of the study by Ceylan et al. (2021).

It has been found that there are significant differences in favor of those who do sports actively in the dimensions of individual causes and motivation for participation in physical activity (total) according to the variable of actively doing sports. In other words, the individual causes and motivation for participation in physical activity (total) scores of those who do sports actively are higher than those who do not actively do sports. This result is partially consistent with the finding of the study by Karaca (2020). On the other hand, according to this variable, it was determined that there was no significant difference in the mean scores of the sub-dimensions of environmental causes and irrationality. In addition, it was found that there was no significant difference in terms of the mean scores of the dimensions of the motivation for participation in physical activity according to the licensed sportsman status and national athlete status variables.

In a study conducted by Arslan, Daskapan and Cakir (2016) to determine the physical activity levels of university students, it was found that 8.5% of female students and 28.1% of male students did enough physical activity. In a meta-analysis study by Plotnikoff et al. (2015) examining the effectiveness of interventions aimed at improving physical activity and nutrition-related behaviors in overweight university students, it was determined that interventions for life behaviors had positive results. In this context, it is thought that the concept of motivation has an important role in the positive results of interventions for life behaviors. In this direction, motivation; it is stated that it is a phenomenon that includes desires, needs, demands and impulses (Cuceloglu, 1996). In this context, it is thought that the concept of motivation has an important role in the positive results of interventions for life behaviors.

In this direction, motivation; it is stated that it is a phenomenon that includes desires, needs, demands and impulses (Cuceloglu, 1996). The individual’s motivation; it can be connected to internal processes such as personal needs, pleasure and curiosities of the hobbies it is related to. In addition, factors outside the individual such as reward, pressure, punishment can motivate the individual (Tekkursun-Demir & Cicioglu, 2018). In this context, individuals can be more easily motivated for different reasons (internal-external) (Ilhan, 2009). Therefore, considering that many factors can be effective on the motivation for participation in physical activity, it is understood that the results obtained within the scope of the research are probable.

As a result, in terms of various variables, the motivation of the students of the faculty of sports sciences to participate in physical activity is described as it exists. In this context, new information has been obtained that will contribute to the literature with the research findings. However, the findings of the study can be diversified by conducting qualitative, experimental and/or mixed studies on the research group with similar characteristics. Within the scope, different results can be obtained that can contribute to the literature.

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